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Main Author Soumya Kanti Datta (DIGI)
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Name	Organisation

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List of abbreviations

App	Application
HMD	Head Mounted Displays
MOOC	Massive Open Online Course
VR	Virtual Reality
WP	Work Package

Executive Summary

Virtual Reality is an emerging technology which has the potential to revolutionise video content delivery to consumers. upPE-T utilises VR as a tool to raise awareness about its novel industrial processes to European citizens (general public, young adults). Six processes of the upPE-T project have been recorded using immersive, 360-degree video and are integrated into a mobile app (called upPE-T VR). This positions upPE-T as one of the cutting edge, innovative arenas where the delivery of research results are performed using Virtual Reality. This deliverable describes the benefits of adopting VR in this project and development of the mobile app. An analysis of VR ecosystem stakeholders is also included to sustain the project result beyond the conclusion of upPE-T.

2. Introduction

Virtual Reality (VR) is a promising and emerging tool for training and awareness development because it offers several advantages over traditional methods [1], [2]. Among them, four key benefits are –

- **Immersion** - VR creates a realistic and immersive environment that can help learners to better understand and retain information. This is especially helpful when the training or awareness session involves industrial processes with complex machineries (like those used in this project).
- **Engagement** - VR experiences are highly engaging, which can lead to improved motivation and learning outcomes.
- **Safety** - VR allows citizens to become aware of industrial processes and learners to practise skills in a safe and controlled environment, without the risk of injury or damage. This is one of the major reasons for selecting VR app as a citizens awareness tool in this project.
- **Flexibility** - VR powered training and awareness can be customized to meet the specific needs of individual learners and organizations.

This deliverable reports an update about the Virtual Reality (VR) mobile app of the upPE-T project. Since all upPE-T processes did not commence at the same time, the VR app presented in previous version of this Deliverable (i.e., D9.12 v1.0) contained immersive 360-degree videos only for two processes (e.g., plastic collection by ECO and enzymatic degradation performed by ECS). During the Year 3 of the project, another four upPE-T processes were recorded as immersive 360-degree videos and these new videos have been added to the upPE-T VR app. Note, the app has been developed for Android powered mobile phones and is primarily targeted for European citizens. The VR video recording and mobile app development tasks are spearheaded by DIGI with design inputs received from TECN at the beginning of the project.

2.1. Context

The upPE-T project methodology (depicted in **Figure 1**) advocates for European citizens' awareness building in WP9 as a guiding principle towards achieving the expected project impacts. The WP9 dedicates Task 9.4 to ideate and develop such awareness tools and the VR mobile app is developed following the ongoing trend of adopting new digital tools for communication, awareness development, and engaging with all stakeholders. Therefore, the VR mobile app is an important tool for the communication roadmap, awareness strategies, and engagement with citizens, hence the overall project methodology.

2.2. Contents and structure

This deliverable reports the upPE-T VR mobile app development process including a co-creation workshop performed with ECO and ECS in April 2022 and the testing phase. Building upon the co-creation workshops, actual 360-degree video recordings were performed close to the end of Year 2. During Year 3, four additional videos were recorded at the premises of the partners – CTCR, MOSES, CETEC, and CETEC-BIO.

All 360-degree, immersive VR videos are available at¹ - https://digiotouchcom-my.sharepoint.com/:f:/g/personal/soumya_digiotouch_com/EnzvdFC4-REt70Td_BgEMoBJLiup_vhO1Pss5HKJ0FEPA?e=qsWESm

¹ European citizens using iPhone can access the videos from this link and play them from an iPhone compatible browser.

The mobile app is available at <https://uppet.eu/citizens-engagement/vr-app>. The Android app is also published in Google Play ensuring that the citizens can download it from the upPE-T website as well as Google Play store.

The structure of the deliverable is as follows. Section 2 briefly introduces the VR technology benefits including 360-degree VR video. Section 3 describes the VR app development process including technical details. The resulting app can be further exploited as a upPE-T project dissemination artefact and its exploitation in other similar use cases. Therefore, DIGI conducted some additional analysis of the VR app stakeholders beyond the upPE-T project which are mentioned in Annex I.

Figure 1 - upPE-T project methodology.

3. Virtual Reality in upPE-T

Virtual reality, an emerging technology, provides an immersive or simulated experience that can be similar or different from the real world. The users generally exploit VR equipment (e.g., HMD, motion controllers) to be able to view a VR content (e.g., a simulated artificial world, a 360-degree image/video of a real-world setting). Although such technology is utilised in medical training and flight simulation purposes, VR has quickly found its utility in many other industry verticals. In the recent past, VR apps have been used as an assistive tool to monitor learning performance of students in a MOOC system [3]. Scalable VR application development has also been researched and reported in existing literature [4].

Over the last decade, new powerful 360-degree cameras and head mounted displays (HMD) (e.g., Apple Vision Pro, Meta Quest) entered the VR ecosystem. It has since reshaped the media landscape, creating new opportunities to provide immersive consumer experiences (e.g., being present at a remote location from the comfort of your own home and able to view 360-degree of the remote location). Standard development organisation W3C responded to this emerging landscape with WebVR² [5] which is now upgraded to consider Extended Reality (XR) and is called WebXR Device API³ which show there is a nascent yet fertile market for the technology.

3.1. 360-degree video

Traditional videography refers to rectangular capture of video using cameras. Compared to that, a 360-degree video utilises specialised omnidirectional cameras capturing a spherical video of a space. The raw footage must then be post-processed (i.e., stitched together) to create an immersive experience for the viewer. Such a video can place the viewer right in the centre of the space (where the recording was performed) to observe the surroundings rather than presenting it to the viewer as an outsider. For this benefit, 360-degree videos are widely used in VR apps. When viewed on mobile phones, the users can simply move their phones in any direction to view corresponding parts of the video capture.

In this project, 360-degree VR videos have been recorded corresponding to the upPE-T upcycling processes and they are displayed through a mobile app developed for Android powered phones. The 360-degree video is an immersive experience for the user. This way, he/she can feel more engaged and stimulated.

² <https://webvr.info/> [Accessed online 8th Oct 2022]

³ <https://www.w3.org/TR/webxr/> [Accessed online 8th Oct 2022]

4. VR mobile app development process

This section concentrates on the VR mobile app co-creation workshops, requirements, and technical implementations.

4.1. Co-creation workshops

During April 2022, DIGI visited the premises of upPE-T partners ECO (in Serbia) and ECS (in Germany) to conduct two internal co-creation workshops about the 360-degree VR video recording (Figure 2). The objectives of these workshops were to understand the individual recording goals of the partners and craft a narrative about their activities that can be understood by the general public and young adults. ECO being involved in PE and PET types of plastics collection, sorting, and shredding, it was jointly decided to film plastic waste disposal in and around the Sava and Danube rivers in Belgrade and the nearby islands. IDI facilitated the co-creation workshop and supported both DIGI and ECO in obtaining permissions required to perform the actual video recording from the city authorities. ECS performs enzymatic degradation of the pre-treated plastics into their building blocks, and it takes place in their laboratory. Therefore, it was decided that the VR video recording will take place at ECS laboratory. Both partners (ECO and ECS) also created a video recording plan and audio transcript (added to the VR video during the post processing of the video). These two workshops have been crucial for finalising the recording timeline, plan, material for recording, and audio transcripts.

A similar approach was taken during the Year 3 with CTCR, MOSES, CETEC, and CETEC-BIO. However, the first set of co-creation workshops also provided a baseline understanding of how to handle the recording timeline, planning, materials for recording, and audio transcript preparation. Therefore, during the Year 3, such co-creation was performed remotely with DIGI leading the efforts while the concerned partners provided the necessary inputs while the video recording took place in the partner premises (Figure 3).

Figure 2 – Pictures from co-creation workshop on VR video recording.

Figure 3 – Pictures from 360-degree video recording sessions in Spain.

4.2. VR app requirements

Despite technological advancements made in the mobile phone industry, adoption of virtual and augmented reality-based apps remains low. One of the biggest barriers to wide adoption of such immersive technologies is the lack of good user experience design. 3D interface design is difficult and expensive, and highly skilled professionals can only address use case specific designs required. However, according to market research agencies⁴, despite being an emerging technology, VR apps show great promise to become the next mainstream computational platform. Keeping in mind such a prevalent scenario, during the requirement and design phase of the app, priority has been given to develop 360-degree VR videos which most of the existing Android powered phones can run without the necessity of additional purchase of head mounted displays or costly mobile phone upgrades/purchases.

The requirements that have been considered are as follows:

⁴ <https://www.computereconomics.com/article.cfm?id=3111> [Access online on 8th Oct 2022].

- The mobile app users do not necessarily need to use an HMD to view the VR videos. But it should be noted that, to have the best experience, users need to consume the videos through the HMD.
- The mobile app will work with Android version 10⁵ onwards.
- The app will work only on landscape mode to provide the best video viewing experience.
- Only 360-degree VR videos of real-life processes will be showcased. Real life processes in upcycling are expected to resonate better with the app users than 3D simulation generated processes.
- The app will be compatible with Meta Quest, Google VR Daydream⁶ 360-degree media specifications.
 - 360-degree videos are stored in the MP4 format encoded with H264.
 - Monoscope videos are recorded with 2:1 aspect ratio.

4.3. VR mobile app software development

During the software development, following features have been developed for the upPE-T VR mobile app.

4.3.1. Authentication

Login is performed using an existing Google account login (as shown in Figure 4) associated with the Android device. This account is already present in the Android powered phones and as a result, the end user does not need to create a new account to access the VR videos through this app. Any two-factor authentication is also taken care of by Google. This makes user experience for login a very easy process for both the end user and reduces the backend software processing performed by DIGI.

Figure 4 – VR mobile app login screen.

4.3.2. VR video consumption

Following a successful login, the user is presented with a screen (shown in Figure 5) where all the upPE-T VR videos are listed sequentially (following the overall process starting with

⁵ <https://www.android.com/android-10/> [Accessed online on 8th Oct 2022].

⁶ Since the first version of upPE-T VR app development, Google VR Daydream has been discontinued. Now in the Year 3, the specification considers compatibility with mobile browsers and Meta Quest HMD.

plastic collection). Users can already check the duration of the video and can select a video to watch on demand.

Figure 5 – VR videos listed in the Android app.

At the end of Year 2, all upPE-T processes did not commence, so only two videos were recorded and delivered through the app. However, other processes were planned to be recorded, so at the end of Year 3, a total of six videos have been released with the updated version of the app.

4.3.3. Terms and conditions of use and notification

The app also lists end user license agreement, privacy policy, and terms and conditions of usage in the app (shown in Figure 6). These terms ensure the developed app meets the ethical and legal guidelines of the European Commission. The users can check these terms from the app itself by going to the settings.

Figure 6 – Tabs to check terms of app usage.

Finally, the app also enables a notification (shown in Figure 7) when new VR videos are available for viewing. This notification can be turned on or off depending on the user preference from the app settings.

Figure 7 – Provision to receive notification for new VR video release.

5. Conclusion

This deliverable serves as an update to the previous version of D9.12 (v1.0) on the European citizens' awareness building VR app. The app has been developed by DIGI and made available to the general public through upPE-T website and Google Play Store. The Android app is continuously maintained and updated by DIGI during the project activities. iPhone users are able to view the videos from a mobile browser. The main goal behind the app is to use it as a communication awareness tool educating the citizens on how the upPE-T processes work. Towards that goal, the communication plan, and activities of WP9 cover promotional activities of the VR mobile app. The KPI related to number of users reached is tracked by Task 9.1 and Task 9.2. The app will be maintained by DIGI beyond the conclusion of the upPE-T project.

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Annex I – VR app stakeholder analysis

To exploit the VR app as widely as possible in addition to the upPE-T project, DIGI performed a wider stakeholder analysis for the app. The list includes –

1. Research, planning
 - a. Academics, R&D
 - b. Publications
 - c. Policy makers and standardization committees
 - d. IP owners
2. Sourcing, pre-production
 - a. Plastics manufacturing
 - b. Enzyme manufacturing
 - c. Factory/Machinery production
 - d. Recycling industries
3. Manufacturing SMEs and large enterprises
4. B2B and B2C focused industries including
 - a. Food and drink industry
 - b. Packaging industry
 - c. Additive manufacturing (3D printing)
 - d. Rubber industry
 - e. Industrial Biotechnology
 - f. Nanotechnology, material science
5. Promoters
 - a. Financially incentivized
 - i. Institutions that finance plastic using industries
 - ii. Governments
 - iii. Marketing agencies
 - iv. Licensing agents, law enforcement agents
 - b. Ecologically incentivized
 - i. Waste management organizations
 - ii. Standardization committees ([CEN and CENELEC](#))
 - iii. Citizens
 - iv. Public health/local government agencies, Policy makers
 - v. Environmentalists spreading awareness (like the upPE-T project partners)